

Protocol for ethical assessment of the submitted TNA proposals

General information

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	based on feedback of WP4 meeting 12 june 2023		modified New role/profile added to the table 1, highlighted in red	
0.2	Updated taking into account the draft of the General Ethical Guidelines (D9.3, V1), the draft of the Harmonisation of access quality management and monitoring procedures for multi-RI TNA (D4.1, V1) and the V1 of D9.1 Project Management Guidelines	15 June 2023	Two new terms in the glossary. Table 1 modified. Figure 2 modified.	11
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Executive Summary

The present deliverable D4.2, “Protocol for ethical assessment of the submitted TNA proposals”, aims at ensuring that the ethical aspects are assessed in a standardized way that meet the requirements of the European Commission (EC) for all TNA proposals submitted to the Agro-Serv consortium calls.

This document is mainly based on deliverable D4.1, “Guidelines on the harmonisation of access quality management” and monitoring procedures for multi-RI TNA and the HORIZON 2020 Manual.

Glossary

Term	Description
Access Manager	Manager of access and service provision in a Research Infrastructure
Access provider	Manage of a specific installation or service within an organisation that is a member of a Research infrastructure
Agro-Serv	The present project
DMP	Data Management Plan : guidelines for management of data within AgroServ
Ethical TA Committee	Composed of representatives on ethical and legal issues from each RI (cf. D4.1)
IEAB	Independent external experts on ethical issues; appointed by the Executive Committee (cf. D9.1)
Installation	Facility or service for the implementation of a specific service, a synonym a facility specifically with respect to access to experimental services
Review Panel	Panel of independent experts that will assess the Transnational Access applications
RI	Research Infrastructure
TNA	Trans-National Access. Allowing third-party researchers from a foreign institution to access an organisation’s research facilities and services.
VA	Virtual Access. Allowing third-party researchers to access an organisation’s cloud, data centre, and/or its other IT facilities and services.
WP	Work Package. A set of related activities within a project.

1 Introduction

In the AgroServ project one of the key instruments is the provision of transnational physical access (TNA), remote and virtual access (VA) to research services that will enable cross-disciplinary research needed for agroecological transition. Several TAVA calls will be launched until the last year of the AgroServ project. The well-known procedures, including quality and ethical ones, at individual RI level need to be harmonisation and standardisation for the multi-RI calls.

D4.2, Protocol for ethical assessment of the submitted TNA proposals, is one of four deliverables to be submitted in WP4, “Access and quality management & Ethics”, and will be implemented in the overall TNA procedure. The procedure described in this document is applicable between the TNA call closure and the starting of the selected projects (Figure 1), and will have an impact on the project assessment and eventual selection:

Figure 1. Milestones in the TNA call and service provision.

This document is the result of several meetings of the members of the Quality management discussion group and the Ethical TNA committee, established in the WP4 and identified in D4.1.

1.1 Objective and scope

The objective is to ensure that the ethical aspects are assessed in a standardized way that meet the requirements of the European Commission (EC) for all TAVA proposals submitted to the Agro-Serv consortium calls, and facilitate communication between all the actors (user, service provider, ethical committees, etc.) in order to reduce as much as possible the time required for achieving ethical compliance.

2 Method

The ethical assessment protocol is applicable on a 2-step submission procedure, as planned in the AgroServ TNA calls, and based on self-assessment questionnaires and feedback from the service providers.

Two self-assessment questionnaires will be used for identifying and handling the ethical/transversal issues related to each project submitted to the TNA call. The questionnaires will be included in the TNA-application procedure, submitted via the ISIA platform.

The following table summarizes who does what, when:

WHEN	WHO	WHAT
Step 1 TNA call	Applicant or PI (eventual user)	1. Answer Questionnaire 1 (Annex 2).
	AgroServ Access Officer	1. Check if the answers are in agreement with AgroServ project self assessment (Annex 1). 2. Identify the ethical/transversal issues based on the requested services / RI, and the answers of the questionnaire 1. 3. Start the ethical procedures if needed.
Step 2 TNA call	Applicant or PI (eventual user)	1. Answer Questionnaire 2 (Annex 3).
	Access Officer(s)	1. Check if the answers are in agreement with AgroServ project self assessment (Annex 1). 2. Forward the questionnaire 2 to the suitable profile (service/facility responsible). 3. Make a check list of ethical/transversal issues that need to be addressed before access provision or in an acceptable time.
	Service/Facility responsible	1. Check, and correct if needed, the answers from the candidate. 2. Give feedback to the access officer(s) on the issues to be dealt with. 3. Start/Complete the internal procedures if needed.
	Ethical TA Committee	1. Approve the Ethic Self-assessment provided at this stage of the call (cf. D9.3 General Ethical Guidelines, V1).
	IEAB	1. If unexpected Ethical Issues arise, provide advice on how to deal with them.
Start of the accepted projects	Access Officer(s)	1. Confirm that the ethical/transversal issues have been addressed in due time (with feedback from the service providers).

A project presented in a TNA call should be in agreement with AgroServ Ethical Self Assessment questionnaire (Annex 1); a project with ethical issues (“yes” answer) different from those previously identified for the AgroServ project will, *a priori*, be rejected. For those projects that are in agreement, Ethical compliance is not an eligibility criteria at the beginning of the TNA call process; since many ethical issues need time to be addressed (ethical committees, authorisations, etc.) and need specific information that will not be available until several

exchanges and feedback between the candidate (IP and eventual user) and the service providers. Nevertheless, based on the results of the questionnaires and the feedback from all the users, the project would be taken into account for the next steps (Step 2, acceptance) of the procedure, or it will be rejected, according to the following Decisional Tree (Figure 2):

Figure 2: Decisional Tree for ethical assessment of TNA projects.

3 References

D4.1 Harmonisation of access quality management and monitoring procedures for multi-RI TNA. Version 1.

D9.1 Project Management Guidelines. Version 1.

D9.3 General Ethical Guidelines. Version 1.

How to complete your ethics self-assessment. Accessible at https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/common/guidance/how-to-complete-your-ethics-self-assessment_en.pdf

4 ANNEXES

4.1 Annex 1. Ethical Self Assessment questionnaire of AgroServ project

Cf. Part A, 4 – Ethics & security, page 541 of AgroServ project.

#	Section	Answer
1	Human Embryonic Stem Cells and Human Embryos	No
2	Humans	No
3	Human Cells / Tissues (not covered by section 1)	No
4	Personal Data	Yes
5	Animals	Yes
6	Non-EU countries	Yes
7	Environment, Health and Safety	Yes
8	Artificial Intelligence	No
9	Other Ethics Issues	No

4.2 Annex 2. Self-assessment questionnaire for the candidates in Step 1 TNA access call

Is the project concerned by one or more of the following Ethics & security issues? (Yes/No)
 Use the HORIZON 2020 Online Manual. Cross-cutting issues. Accessible at https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/cross-cutting-issues/ethics_en.htm for further information.

#	Section	Answer
1	Human Embryonic Stem Cells and Human Embryos	Yes / No
2	Humans	Yes / No
3	Human Cells / Tissues (not covered by section 1)	Yes / No
4	Personal Data	Yes / No
5	Animals	Yes / No
6	Non-EU countries	Yes / No
7	Environment, Health and Safety	Yes / No
8	Artificial Intelligence	Yes / No
9	Other Ethics Issues	Yes / No

Only the projects that answer No to all, or those answering Yes to one or more of the following Sections, are eligible. The others are not in coherence with AgroServ self-assessment questionnaire (Annex 1).

4	Personal Data
5	Animals
6	Non-EU countries
7	Environment, Health and Safety

4.3 Annex 3. Self-assessment questionnaire for the candidates in Step 2 TNA access call

For the issues already identified in Step 1 (“yes” answers for one or more of the Sections in agreement with AgroServ self-assessment questionnaire), please specify by answering to the Ethics & security issues concerned? (Yes/No)

Use the HORIZON 2020 Online Manual. Cross-cutting issues. Accessible at https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/cross-cutting-issues/ethics_en.htm for further information.

#	Section	Answer
4	Personal Data	
	Does this activity involve processing of personal data?	Yes / No
	Does it involve the processing of special categories of personal data (e.g.: genetic, biometric and health data, sexual lifestyle, ethnicity, political opinion, religious or philosophical beliefs)?	Yes / No
	Does it involve profiling, systematic monitoring of individuals, or processing of large scale of special categories of data or intrusive methods of data processing (such as, surveillance, geolocation tracking etc.)?	Yes / No
	Does this activity involve further processing of previously collected personal data (including use of preexisting data sets or sources, merging existing data sets)?	Yes / No
	Is it planned to export personal data from the EU to non-EU countries? Specify the type of personal data and countries involved	Yes / No
	Is it planned to import personal data from non-EU countries into the EU or from a non-EU country to another non-EU country? Specify the type of personal data and countries involved	Yes / No
5	Animals: Does this activity involve animals?	
	Are they vertebrates?	Yes / No
	Are they non-human primates? (NHP)	Yes / No
	Are they genetically modified?	Yes / No
	Are they cloned farm animals?	Yes / No
6	Non-EU countries	
	Will some of the activities be carried out in non-EU countries?	Yes / No
	In case non-UE countries are involved, do the activities undertaken in these countries raise potential ethics issues?	Yes / No
	Is it planned to use local resources (e.g. animal and/or human tissue samples, genetic material, live animals, human remains, materials of historical value, endangered fauna or flora samples, etc.)?	Yes / No
	Is it planned to import any material (other than data) from non-EU countries into the EU or from a non-EU country to another non-EU country? For data imports, see section 4.	Yes / No
	Is it planned to export any material (other than data) from the EU to non-EU countries? For data exports, see section 4.	Yes / No
	Does this activity involve low and/or lower middle income countries, (if yes, detail the benefit-sharing actions planned in the self-assessment)	Yes / No
7	Environment, Health and Safety	
	Does this activity involve the use of substances or processes that may cause harm to the environment, to animals or plants.(during the implementation of the activity or further to the use of the results, as a possible impact) ?	Yes / No
	Does this activity deal with endangered fauna and/or flora / protected areas?	Yes / No
	Does this activity involve the use of substances or processes that may cause harm to humans, including those performing the activity.(during the implementation of the activity or further to the use of the results, as a possible impact) ?	Yes / No